

Generations and Gender Survey (Round II)

Wave 2 Questionnaire

User module “Global Uncertainty and Institutional Trust”

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Please cite as: Andersson, G., Neyer, G., Lappegård, T., & Bujard, M. (2024). User module: "Global Uncertainty and Institutional Trust" (GGG-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044105

User Modules in the GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire

The GGS-II Wave 2 questionnaire was restructured to include new thematic sections, with space allocated for user-driven innovations. In 2023, an open call invited researchers to submit new content modules. The proposals were evaluated by a selection committee based on their scientific novelty and relevance to the GGS.

Five user modules were selected and integrated into the questionnaire, offering fresh insights into family dynamics, fertility, and related topics. This working paper series contains revised versions of the original submissions, including the finalized questions that were ultimately incorporated into the Wave 2 questionnaire.

Andersson, G., Neyer, G., Lappegård, T., & Bujard, M. (2024). *User module: "Global Uncertainty and Institutional Trust"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044105

Berrington, A., & Perelli-Harris, B. (2024). *User module: "Leaving and Returning to the Parental Home"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044047

Billingsley, S., Mollborn, S., Olah, L., & Duvander, A.-Z. (2024). *User module: "Intensive Parenting"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14043910

Mortelmans, D., Lück, D., Claessens, E., Van Gasse, D., Bujard, M., & Frembs, L. (2024). *User module: "Singlehood"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044075

Rouvroye, L., Fischer, M., Rampazzo, F., van der Vleuten, M., Fortes De Lena, F., Pao, C., de Vries, L., & Jin, Y. (2024). *User module: "Sexual Orientation"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044062

Abstract

The purpose of the proposed survey items is to cover some elements that we consider related to increasing global uncertainties and decreasing levels of trust during the last decade, and which we think are related to ongoing and recent fertility change in Europe and much of the developed world. The survey items have been developed by a working group consisting of demographers in the five Nordic and some other countries and have been implemented in the existing GGSs in several Nordic countries. Research results of the items have been presented at international demography conferences. A slightly reduced version of the survey items has been approved for incorporation into the German GGS organized by FReDA.

The module introduces a novel and so far lacking perspective of subjective considerations to fertility and family research and contributes a core generational dimension to the GGS. The inclusion the survey items in the GGS of all GGP countries makes a powerful basis for comparative research on the role of uncertainties and trust in current demographic developments. For the countries that already included these survey items in the previous survey round, it offers the opportunity to follow developments of changing subjective considerations across time.

Motivation and scientific foundation

The survey items have been developed by a working group consisting of demographers in the five Nordic and some other countries, all of which had either carried out the GGS or planned to do so. The working group relied on survey items that had been tested and implemented in other national or comparative survey and scrutinized their applicability and usefulness for the GGS. The survey items have been implemented in the existing GGSs in several Nordic countries and in Estonia. Most recently, a slightly reduced version of the survey items has been approved for incorporation into the German GGS organized by FReDA. The module introduces a novel and so far lacking perspective of subjective considerations to fertility and family research, and it also adds a new generational dimension to the GGS. The inclusion of the survey items in the GGS of all GGP countries makes a powerful basis for comparative research on the role of uncertainties and trust in current demographic developments. For the countries that already included these survey items in the previous survey round, it offers the opportunity to follow developments of changing subjective considerations across time.

The proposed items capture global events that have occurred or increased and gained intensified attention during the past two decade. Theoretically, the items connect (a) to Beck's and Giddens' proposition that societies move towards "world risk societies" in which individual and collective decisions, agency and behaviour are increasingly shaped by global (transnational) risks. These risks affect also people's trust in institutions. The items also connect to the new demographic theories on "perceived economic uncertainty", proposed by Vignoli and colleagues. The implementation of our global uncertainty and trust items in the GGS will empirically and theoretically advance fertility and family research in that they connect fertility and family issues to global events and their perception. This enables researchers to place fertility and family issues in a broader, transnational and future-oriented perspective. Given the so far unexpected and unexplained recent decline of fertility to very low or even lowest-low fertility levels in many developed countries, this module is highly significant not only for demographic research, but also for policy makers by showing to what extent global events are significant for fertility and family development.

Relevance to GGS-II wave 2 and all countries

The module adds a forward-looking perspective to the retrospective perspective of the GGS wave 2. It also adds a necessary context-related aspect to GGS wave 2 and allows for in-depth analyses as well as connections to other methods to study fertility and family development.

Survey questions

UNCintro (*Uncertainty intro*) (Empty)

We would like to ask you some questions on how you perceive the world around you.

b16UNC01 (*Unc01 intro*) (Empty)

Thinking about the future, how much does the following worry you?

b16UNC01A (*Terrorism*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Terrorism

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01B (*Climate change*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Climate change

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01C (*Overpopulation*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Overpopulation

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01D (*Economic crisis*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Economic crises

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01E (*Increased number of refugees*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Increased number of refugees

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01F (*High unemployment*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

High unemployment

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01G (*Organised crime*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Organised crime

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01H (*Military conflicts*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Military conflicts

Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01I (*Global epidemics*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Global epidemics
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01J (*Weakened democracy*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Weakened democracy
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01K (*Increased social inequality*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Increased social inequality
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01L (*Political extremism*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Political extremism
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01M (*Future generations' prospect*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Prospect of future generations
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC02 (*b16UNC02 intro*) (*Empty*)

The next questions ask your opinion about different institutions in 18;. How much confidence do you have in the way the following institutions and groups do their job?

b16UNC02A (*The government*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The government
Very high trust
Quite high trust
Neither high nor low trust
Quite low trust
Very low trust

b16UNC02B (*The police*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The police
Very high trust
Quite high trust
Neither high nor low trust
Quite low trust
Very low trust

b16UNC02C (*Medical services*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Medical services

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02D (*The civil service*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The civil service

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02E (*News media*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

News media

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02F (*The EU*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The EU

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16ATT01 (*General trusta (att01)*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Generally speaking, would you say that most people can be trusted or that you need to be very careful in dealing with people?

Most people can be trusted

Need to be very careful

b16UNC03B (*General trust_b*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Do you think that most people would try to take advantage of you if they got a chance or would they try to be honest and fair?

Would take advantage

Would try to be honest and fair

b16UNC04 (*Optimism*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Optimists are people who look to the future with confidence and who mostly expect good things to happen. How would you describe yourself? How optimistic are you in general? Please express your opinion on a scale of 1 to 5.

1 Not at all optimistic

2

3

4

5 Very optimistic

b16UNC05 (*Risk taking*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Would you describe yourself as someone who tries to avoid risk (risk averse) or someone who likes to take chances (a risk taker)?

Please express your opinion on a scale of 1 to 5.

1 Risk averse

2

3

4

5 Risktaker

References

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